

IV. TuşnadEcoBear
conf
Book of Abstracts

21-24 October 2025
Băile Tuşnad
Romania

IV. TusnadEcoBear Conference Contacts

Event organisation, venue, accommodation, logistics and program:

István Imecs - Project Bag Association
E-mail: asociatiaprojectbag@gmail.com
Tel: +40 743 775 213

Scientific content, speakers, and topics (until 08.2025):

Alexandra Sallay-Mosoi - WWF Romania
E-mail: asallay@wwf.ro
Tel: +40 728 424 667

Coordination of CoCo project conference participation and workshop chairman:

Mihai I. Pop
E-mail: popmihai@icdcrm.ro
Tel: +40 740 201 079

Content and editing of the Book of Abstracts:

Nándor Erős
E-mail: erosnandi@gmail.com
Tel: +40 756 306 431

Moderator:

Radu Pircă
E-mail: radupirca@gmail.com

Revised by: Members of TusnadEcoBear Team

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IV. TusnadEcoBear Conference

21 - 24 October 2025
Hotel O3Zone, Aleea Sfânta Ana 2
Băile Tuşnad 535100, Romania

Welcome Address

A conference about people and bears, about coexistence.

The aim of the event is to bring together a variety of views, competences and experiences from various experts from Europe and beyond, on the topic of human-large carnivore coexistence. The discussions shall foster the generation of practical and viable solutions for reducing human-wildlife conflicts in human dominated landscapes. The conference seeks to identify the current level of knowledge regarding the management of brown bear populations across Europe, as well as best and negative practices. The interaction between key international experts and young participants is highly encouraged in order to build capacity in terms of coping with future challenges (including the ones derived from climate change).

The conference is organised as part of the CERV project (101146879) "Coexisting with bears - Conservation needs Conversation!" funded by the European Union and implemented with the support of the ProjectBag Association (Destination Management Unit - Băile Tuşnad and Surroundings ecotourism destination), Mayor's Office of Băile Tuşnad, WWF-Romania, WWF Bulgaria, WWF Hungary, BOKU University, Austria) and New Horizons Bulgaria.

The conference is also supported by:

- the "TusnadEcoBear: Connect & Conserve" project, which receives funding from Bears in Mind foundation;
- the "Co-creating coexistence: Advancing policies, practices, and stakeholder engagement for integrating wildlife and livestock into sustainable multi-functional landscapes in Europe" project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe – Research and Innovation programme (grant agreement No. 101181958);
- the Harghita County Council through the Csomád-Bálványos Intercommunity Development Association.

Respectfully,

TusnadEcoBear Team

István Imecs (Project Bag Association, Romania)
+40 743 775 213
imecs.istvan17@gmail.com

Funded by
the European Union

Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme (CERV)
Coexisting with bears Conservation needs Conversation!

CERV COEXISTENCE – PROJECT SUMMARY

“Coexisting with bears – Conservation needs Conversation!” (GA-Nr. 101146879)

Across EU member states, large-carnivore management is becoming increasingly challenging as both human safety and the conservation of wildlife populations have to be considered. There is a lack of a clear long-term vision for achieving and maintaining coexistence between humans and bears in many Eastern European countries, where human-bear conflicts are frequent. Rural communities are those actually affected and often ignored by the state authorities and other relevant stakeholders when it comes to establishing and implementing coexistence management plans. Therefore this project aims to foster participatory decision-making and collaborative management among the key stakeholders from 3 pilot countries (Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary) under the umbrella of academic knowledge and guidance (Austria) while promoting and ensuring active community engagement (local/regional community and general public) to provide guidelines for sustainable coexistence plans that go beyond changing political positions of local and state authorities. Thus, the project seeks to foster a sense of ownership and shared responsibility for brown bear conservation. Special attention will be paid to youth education and engagement to increase understanding, knowledge about human-bear conflict and the species management, while building empathy and support for bears in the upcoming decision-making generation. At present, policy debates and decision-making processes around coexistence with bears are conducted with a poor share of democratic/intercultural competence in traditionally patriarchal societies, thus the project targets the pro-active participation of marginalized groups such as women and ethnic and religious minorities. Lessons learned and best practices will be shared at the national and European levels and it will make sure that activities implemented remain operative and efficient after the project ends. This project contributes substantially to the implementation of EU and national policies.

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/cerv>

Project financed by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are entirely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union, which cannot be held responsible for them. **CONSENT FOR THE PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA** The operators of personal data are: Association WWF Romania and Association Cutia de Proiecte – Project Bag in partnership with Băile Tușnad City Hall. The purpose of the processing: conducting and promoting the project entitled "Coexistence with bears - Conservation needs conversation!", monitoring the fulfillment of its objectives, implementing, managing and monitoring the non-refundable financing contract, reporting the results and submitting the supporting documents for achieving the object of the non-refundable financing contract, carrying out quantitative and qualitative studies in order to evaluate the effects and impact of the project. Transfer of personal data: These personal data between data operators and third parties can be transmitted within the European Economic Area, especially on the territory of Romania, Belgium, Hungary, Bulgaria, Austria. In addition, these personal data may be transferred to the following categories of persons: financier, evaluators and/or auditors on the occasion of the controls carried out by them at the request of the financier, tax authorities and other public authorities in case of a potential control on their part. I understand and agree that I will not receive any monetary or other compensation for these photos/videos or recordings. The policy regarding the processing of personal data can be consulted at: <https://gdpr.eu/>

Program

IV. TusnadEcoBearConf

Monday – 20 October

18:00 **Welcome - Icebreaker (Hotel O3Zone) - "Ion Creangă" conference room**
Address: Aleea Sfânta Ana 2, Băile Tuşnad 535100

Tuesday – 21 October

8:00 - 09:30 **Registration (Hotel O3Zone)**

09:30 - 10:00 **Conference opening and introduction (EN/RO)**

"Mihai Eminescu" Conference Room

Session 1: Carnivore Conservation in Multi-Use Landscapes

- 10:00 - 11:00 **John D. C. Linnell (Norway) - Keynote Speaker (Professor at the University of Inland Norway and Senior scientist at the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research)**
- 11:00 - 11:20 Silvia Borlea (Romania): Impact of Land Use on Wildlife-Vehicle Collisions in Romania
- 11:20 - 11:40 Jörg Fabian Knufinke (Austria): Wolves in Austria – Modelling Socio-Economic Conflict and Habitat Potential to Inform Coexistence
- 11:40 - 12:00 Robin Rigg (Slovakia): Co-Creating Coexistence in Shared Landscapes
- 12:00 - 12:30 **Coffee break / Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction**
- 12:30 - 12:50 Roman Cherepanyn (Ukraine): Telemetry Study of the Eurasian Lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Rivnenskyi Nature Reserve: First Insights Into Lynx Home Ranges in Ukraine - online
- 12:50 - 13:10 Dagmar Mirzoev, Lucie Baránková (Czech Republic): Current State of Harmonizing Monitoring, Conflict Prevention, and Anti-Poaching in the Carpathians: Insights from the 'Setting the Scene' Phase
- 13:10 - 13:30 Anna Steluta Manolache (Romania): A Structured Taxonomy and Decision-Making Framework for Human-Bear Interactions in Romania
- 13:30 - 13:50 Martin Duľa (Czech Republic): Project LECA – Supporting the Coexistence and Conservation of Carpathian Large Carnivores: Preliminary Outcomes from Monitoring and Conflict prevention Efforts Targeting Wolves and Bears in the Beskydy-Kysuce and Tatra Pilots
- 13:50 - 15:20 **Lunch break (Hotel restaurant) / Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction**
- 15:20 - 15:40 Michal Haring (Slovakia): Improving Human-Bear Coexistence: Testing of Bear-Resistant Solutions in Slovakia
- 15:40 - 16:00 Sybille Klenzendorf (Germany): Test Results for Piloting SMART Conservation Software for Human-Wildlife Conflict Monitoring
- 16:00 - 16:20 Enache Costin (Romania): Monitoring Eurasian Lynx Population Using Camera Trapping in the Southern Carpathians of Romania
- 16:20 - 16:40 Szabó Szilárd (Romania): Characteristics of Bear-Related Damage Assessment in Harghita County
- 16:40 - 17:00 Alice Ouvrier (France): What Pastoralism and Bears Share: When Humans and Animals Shape Landscapes of Coexistence

- 17:00 - 17:10 Poster section**
 Eliana Sevianu (Romania): Recolonization of Grey Wolves in Human-Dominated Transylvanian Landscapes: Land-Use Change, Coexistence, and Sustainable Development
 Robin Rigg (Slovakia): Carnivore Damage Prevention News (CDPnews)
- 17:10 - 17:30 Coffee break / Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction**

"Petöfi Sándor" Conference Room

Session 2: Carnivore Ecology in a Changing World: Climate and Habitat Challenges

- 17:30 - 18:30 Cristian-Remus Papp (Romania) - Keynote Speaker (Wildlife and Landscapes National Manager, WWF-Romania / Associate Lecturer, Babes-Bolyai University)**
- 18:30 - 18:50 Máthé István (Romania): The Impact of Climate Change on Surface Waters of Large Carnivore Habitats in Szeklerland (Romania)**
- 18:50 - 19:10 Ágnes Keresztesi (Romania): Climate Change in Romania and Implications for Ecosystems**

19:30 Dinner - "Mihai Eminescu" conference room

Wednesday – 22 October

8:00 - 09:00 Registration (Hotel O3Zone)

"Mihai Eminescu" Conference Room

Session 3: Hunting, Population Management and Conservation: Balancing Ethics & Management Needs

- 9:00 - 10:00 Klemen Jerina (Slovenia) - Keynote Speaker (Professor at the University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Department For Forestry and Renewable Forest Resources)**
- 10:00 - 10:20 Andra Neagu (Romania): Wildlife at Risk: A Media-Based Analysis of Wildlife Poaching in Romania**
- 10:20 - 10:40 Mihai I. Pop (Romania): The Illusion of Optimum: Why Habitat Scores Are Unreliable for Brown Bear Management Decisions?**

10:40 - 11:10 Coffee break / Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction

Session 4: Local Community and Local Economy Roles in Carnivore Conservation

- 11:10 - 12:10 Özgün Emre Can (Turkey) - Keynote Speaker (Assistant Professor at Ankara University, Department of Biology)**
- 12:10 - 12:30 Emese Kozma-Kis (Romania): From Education to Action: Youth Empowerment and Community Participation in Human–Wildlife Coexistence**
- 12:30 - 12:50 Michal Feller (Czech Republic): From Data to Dialogue: The Role of Volunteer Monitoring in Large Carnivore Conservation**
- 12:50 - 13:10 István Szabó (Romania): Collaborative Development of a Bear Smart Touristic Business Plan**
- 13:10 - 13:30 Brady Mattsson (Austria): Beyond Reinvention: Toward Transparent Decisions for Community Engagement in Bear Conservation**

13:30 - 14:40 Lunch break (Hotel restaurant)/ Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction

- 14:40 - 15:00 Romana Uhrinová (Czech Republic): Between Fear and Fascination: Attitudes Toward Wolves, Bears, and Lynx in Czech Borderlands**
- 15:00 - 15:20 Ovidiu Stancu (Romania): Captive Bear Dilemma**
- 15:20 - 15:40 Michal Haring (Slovakia): Brown Bear Conservation in Slovakia: The Rising Role of NGOs and Scientists**
- 15:40 - 16:00 István Imecs (Romania): Empowering youth for human–large carnivore coexistence: education and engagement outcomes**
- 16:00 - 16:20 Coffee break / Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction**

Session 5: Camera Traps, AI and Drones: The Future of Carnivore Research and Conflict Prevention

- 16:20 - 17:20 **Dimitris Bormpoudakis (Greece) - Keynote Speaker (Callisto - Wildlife and Nature Conservation Society): Keynote Presentation: Emergent Technologies for Human–Wildlife Coexistence**
- 17:20 - 17:40 Ruben Iosif (Romania): Wolf Population Size and Composition in One of Europe's Strongholds, the Romanian Carpathians
- 17:40 - 18:00 Cosmin-Andrei Conțu (Romania): RO-BEAR: A Year of Progress in Bear Sighting Monitoring
- 18:00 - 18:20 Claudiu Olenici (Romania): AnimAlert Digital Platform – Between Citizen Science and Stakeholders' Actions
- 18:20 - 18:40 László Gál (Romania): Does Supplementary Feeding Affect Brown Bear Habituation and Human–Bear Conflicts?

"Petőfi Sándor" conference room

- 18:45 - 20:00 Panel discussion: Is Human–Bear Coexistence Feasible Under the Current Human Landscape Domination?
Part 1. Authority perspective (RO)
Part 2. Civil, academic, national park's and LCIE perspective (EN)

20:00 Dinner - "Mihai Eminescu" conference room

Thursday – 23 October: Field trip & on-site Workshop

- 9:30 - 10:30 Departure by bus to the Mohos Peat Bog – Lake Saint Anne Natura 2000 site (ROSCI0248).
- 10:30 - 10:45 Reception by **Levente Dósa** (Executive Director of the Pro Szent Anna Association and the Director of the Administration of Saint Anne Lake and the Mohos Peat Bog) in the parking area, followed by a brief introduction of the visitor center
- 10:45 - 13:00 **István Szabó** (Foundation Conservation Carpathia, Romania): Knowledge-sharing workshop on bear-smart business plans (location: visitor center)
- 13:00 - 14:00 **Lunch on site (location: visitor center)**
- 14:00 - 17:00 **Levente Dósa**, guided tour: Mohos Peat Bog and Saint Anne Lake, as well as the particularities of the daily coexistence with bears
- 17:00 - 18:00 Return trip by bus to the Hotel O3Zone (Address: Aleea Sfânta Ana 2, Băile Tușnad 535100)
- 19:00 - 02:00 **Gala dinner**
Live concert, wine & snacks (Tulip restaurant and event hall)
We will provide a welcome package for everyone in attendance, which includes wine, spirits, water, soft drinks, and appetizers. Afterward, additional drinks can be purchased at the bar.
Address: 50 meters from the O3Zone hotel (restaurantlaleaua.com)

Friday – 24 October: Workshop day - Participation is by invitation only, whereas the audience may attend freely

"Petőfi Sándor" Conference Room

Workshop 1. - Main language: EN	Brady Mattsson & Jörg Fabian Knufinke (Institute of Wildlife Biology and Game Management, BOKU University, Austria): Stakeholder Workshop - Brown Bear Management
9:30 - 10:00	Registration & Welcome Coffee
10:00 - 10:15	Workshop opening and introductory presentation
10:15 - 11:15	Interactive session
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch break (Hotel restaurant)/ Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction
14:00 - 15:30	Interactive session
15:30 - 16:00	Conclusions & EU survey

"Mihai Eminescu" Conference Room

Workshop 2. - Main language: RO	Mihai I. Pop (Research and Development Institute for Wildlife and Mountain Resources, Miercurea Ciuc, Romania): Designing Potential Scenarios for Collaboration Between Pastoralism and Wildlife Management
9:00 - 9:30	Registration & Welcome Coffee
9:30 - 10:00	Presentation of CoCo project & Workshop goal
10:00 - 10:20	Presentation of the Methodology
10:20 - 10:50	Interactive session part (1) – Individual work
10:50 - 11:20	Coffee break
11:20 - 13:00	Interactive session part (2) – Group work
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch break (Hotel restaurant)/ Networking / Art for Coexistence – Exhibition & Auction

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Telemetry Study of the Eurasian Lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Rivnenskyi Nature Reserve: First Insights Into Lynx Home Ranges in Ukraine

Roman Cherepanyn^{1,2*}, Mykhailo Franchuk³, Jakub Kubala⁴, Yuriy Andreychuk⁵, Ihor Dykyy^{2,6},
Taras Yamelynets^{2,5}

21 Oct
2025
12:30

- ¹ Vasyl Stefanyk Carpathian National University, Biology and Ecology Department, Taras Shevchenko Street 54, 76018 Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine
² WWF-Ukraine, Wildlife team, Raisy Okipnoi Street 4, office 170, 02002 Kyiv, Ukraine
³ Nature Reserve "Rivnenskyi", Scientific-Research Department, "Dubky tract" Street 1, Chudel village, Sarny District, 34542 Rivne Region, Ukraine
⁴ Technical University in Zvolen, Department of Applied Zoology and Wildlife Management, T. G. Masaryka Street 24, 96001 Zvolen, Slovakia
⁵ Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Faculty of Geography, Universytetska Street 1, 79000 Lviv, Ukraine
⁶ Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Zoology Department, Universytetska Street 1, 79000 Lviv, Ukraine

* e-mail: rcherepanyn@wwf.ua
roman.cherepanyn@pnu.edu.ua
roman.cherepanyn@gmail.com

Currently, in Ukraine, there is practically no real experimental assessment of the spatial structure of the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*), the size of its home ranges, and the ecological limitation of the species to certain areas based on telemetric data. Information on the spatial structure of the lynx population is important for a better understanding of the species' ecology and for improving the effectiveness of lynx management and protection in nature conservation and economic territories within various landscape complexes. Therefore, the task of the work is to study and evaluate the lynx home ranges and the peculiarities of its ecology within the Polissia region in Ukraine based on GPS-GSM telemetry data. Work on the temporary removal of lynx individuals from nature for the installation of a GPS-GSM telemetry collar of the "Ecotone" company was carried out on the territory of the Nature Reserve "Rivnenskyi" (Polissia region of Ukraine). The temporary removal of the lynx was carried out by the method of catching an individual in a box trap. As a result of the operation of the box trap, on February 4, 2023, it was possible to catch a sexually mature (4-5 years old) male lynx weighing 22 kg, and after appropriate manipulations according to the protocol, the animal was successfully released. The animal was briefly anaesthetised for collar placement in accordance with international veterinary protocols. It was possible to obtain telemetry data from the collar (487 GPS coordinates) for the period from February 4, 2023, to August 6, 2023. The device worked in the mode of fixing 4 locations per day with an interval of 6 hours between each. Later, due to a technical malfunction, the device stopped sending GPS locations. The obtained data were evaluated monthly, seasonally (spring, summer), during the mating and non-mating periods and for the entire observation period. Spatial-temporal geodata of the GPS tracker were processed using ESRI ArcGIS Pro 3.2.2 licensed software. The lynx's average annual home range varied between 258 and 351 km², depending on the estimator applied (100% MCP, AKDE, KDE). Clear seasonal differences were observed, with larger ranges in the non-mating period (246 km², 100% MCP) and smaller ranges in the mating period (160 km², 100% MCP). *Capreolus capreolus*, *Sus scrofa*, *Lepus europaeus*, *Castor fiber* and *Tetrastes bonasia* are noted in the lynx male's diet. Cases of elimination of *Vulpes vulpes* and *Nyctereutes procyonoides* as trophic competitors are observed. 30.5% of all telemetric observations of lynxes were recorded within nature conservation areas, and 69.5% were recorded in economic territories. Our results correspond to trends observed in other European lynx populations, yet they also demonstrate region-specific variations influenced by local environmental features. The data obtained on the male lynx in the Polissia region of Ukraine provide valuable insights into the species' ecology and contribute to the effective management and conservation of lynx populations. Future telemetry studies in the Ukrainian Carpathians are essential to enable comparative analyses of spatial parameters between Baltic and Carpathian lynx populations.

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